

Improving CNN approaches for upscaling techniques: Comparing traditional upscaling methods, new solution based on meliorated genetic algorithm and convolutional auto-encoders

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Abstract

High resolution models representing the heterogeneity of oil reservoirs can rarely be used directly in reservoir simulation due to the high computational cost involved. Hence, it is necessary to perform upscaling procedures to transform high resolution models to computational grids. However, the complexity for computing upscaled properties is also an important factor since the coarsening method should accurately capture the fine scale heterogeneity. In order to reduce the computational time of the upscaling stage, recently we proposed a methodology that incorporates a convolutional neural network (CNN), automatically designed by our genetic algorithm (GA), to predict the equivalent permeability. In this paper we go two steps further aiming to better position our CNN approach inside the upscaling subject and to improve it. To achieve the first goal, we compare traditional upscaling techniques in order to select

the best one to compare with our CNN approach. We have noticed in the literature that the comparison between upscaling techniques has been made based on a very limited number of samples taken from benchmarks. Consequently, we carefully perform this step by considering a more complete experimental setup that includes 50 channelized layers (from 36 to 85) from the SPE10 model besides synthetic realizations with regions of high permeability. Considering the computational cost, average relative error over the production profile, and breakthrough time, the local procedure was selected as the best one. With this technique, we generated 2D and 3D datasets to select the best CNN architectures via GA. Such architectures provided results that converged to the reference solution in the fine mesh. In order to improve our methodology (second goal), we incorporated in the GA algorithm a novel initialization method, computed from the probability distribution of the weights adjusted in previous generations, with the aim of designing more efficient architectures. We also developed a CNN-based autoencoder, designed to compute the coarse-scale permeability in the reduced space from the encoder whose structure is generated by the GA, obtaining better upscaling results than the same CNN trained outside the autoencoder.

Keywords: Permeability, Upscaling, Convolutional Neural Networks, Genetic Algorithm

1 Introduction

The simulation of fluid production processes in geological formations is an important tool for predicting oil production and reservoir management. However, simulations on the scale where heterogeneities occur demand a large amount of computational resources to obtain an accurate prediction of production curves. A primary input to the simulator is the geological model commonly built geostatistically and containing petrophysical properties constrained to data of different types and scales [1]. This model generally requires fine scale descriptions of reservoir porosity and permeability in grids of tens of millions of cells to adequately capture the spatial variability that impacts the fluid flow and transport behavior [2, 3]. Despite increasing processing power and intense research into computational techniques, reservoir simulators can rarely run simulations directly on highly detailed models due to memory constraints and/or processing time [1, 4, 5]. To be feasible to execute these simulations, it is necessary to perform the upscaling procedures to transform high resolution models to computational grids such that important small scale features are captured [4, 6, 7]. As a consequence, this procedure allows multiple simulations to be carried out with less computational effort to quantify the uncertainty attributed to the performance of the reservoir [7]. However, excessive upscaling leads to loss of information that directly affects the accuracy of the result

and, therefore, there is a need to maintain a balance between simulation accuracy and scale up ratio [8]. In scale up process, the properties assigned to small scale cells are replaced with a constant and smoothed quantity over the region of interest which contains fewer details at the larger scale. The quality of this process is usually assessed by comparing the production profile of the upscaled model with the reference solution on the fine grid.

The need to compute upscaled properties has motivated the development of many techniques, ranging from analytical methods to a variety of numerical approaches [2, 9, 10]. Despite not requiring a lot of computational resources, analytical methods (e.g., arithmetic, harmonic and geometric averaging) are not as accurate as numerical methods (e.g., single-phase and two-phase flow methods), especially for highly heterogeneous reservoirs. The flow-based techniques can be classified as local, extended local, global or quasi-global, depending of the solution domain over which the flow simulation is performed for the calculation of the coarse scale quantities [3, 4]. In local approaches, upscaled parameters are computed using only the fine scale regions corresponding to the target cell in the coarse scale. In extended local procedures, the coarsened quantities are calculated considering not only the regions that correspond to the target cell but a border region around those regions is also considered. Both of these methods require assumptions regarding the boundary conditions to be imposed, which can lead to inaccuracy in some cases. On the other hand, global methods perform fine scale flow simulation over the entire domain to determine the coarse scale parameters [3, 11]. These methods may achieve high degrees of accuracy but have the drawback of requiring high computational cost for global fine scale solutions. The quasi-global approaches are less computationally demanding than the global procedures, using approximate coarse scale flow information to perform the scale transfer. However, these techniques are preferable when the full global fine scale simulation is prohibitive. They are easily parallelizable and decrease the occurrence of non-positive upscaled quantities, providing accurate result without solving any global fine scale problems. Despite its advantages, they are significantly expensive for large problems.

To reduce the high time consumption of reservoir simulation, the deep learning methods can be explored as an alternative, allowing simulations to be executed and answers to be produced with the agility that the industry requires. In addition, the techniques also can help to bridge the gap between the simulation and geological grids. This will entail a big leap to reservoir simulation and could simplify reservoir management workflow considerably. In order to reduce the computational requirements of reservoir simulations, we proposed in [12] a framework for the prediction of low resolution permeability models via convolutional neural networks (CNNs) automatically designed by a genetic algorithm (GA). In this methodology, a GA method that explores the concept of transfer learning is developed to calibrate the CNN architecture to incorporate the effects of fine scale geological variations on macroscale models, being flexible for use in different scenarios. In [12], the CNN approach was compared

with the local upscaling technique obtaining outstanding results regarding the root mean square error (RMSE), with lower computational demand.

Hence, in the current upscaling scenario, besides the already mentioned analytical and numerical categories of upscaling techniques, our work presented in [12] includes a CNN methodology. So, it is imperative to perform a deep comparison between those upscaling methodologies to better position our CNN approach inside the upscaling area. However, such comparison does not follow the traditional workflow for comparing upscaling methods. The particularity in this case is that the CNN works as a surrogate model meaning that it can compute low-resolution permeability fields if trained with data generated with a reference model. Consequently, firstly, we must select the best upscaling technique among the traditional (analytical and numerical) approaches. Next, this technique is used to generate the CNN training and validation sets for the permeability upscaling problem.

Therefore, the first point in our research is to assemble a set of traditional methods considering works that present comparisons between upscaling methods. In this line, we consider the works [3, 4, 7, 13–17] published since 2001. We analyzed those works looking for methods that are commonly used for computing large scale quantities and that serve as baselines for the development of new techniques. Based on such criteria, we have selected the following traditional upscaling methods: arithmetic averaging [18], local [6], local-extended [19] and local-global [3]. Additionally, the former is fast, easy to implement, but less efficient than the other ones. In contrast, the local and local-extended techniques are more precise and more expensive than the arithmetic averaging. Moreover, they are not able to adequately capture fine-scale features for highly heterogeneous reservoirs. The local-global technique is more efficient in this scenario, but it requires a high computational cost than the remaining methods.

Another important point that emerges from the analysis of the literature, is that the comparison between upscaling techniques has been made based on a very limited number of samples taken from benchmarks like SPE10 model [13], and Stanford V dataset [20]. This issue is critical for our work because our idea is to demonstrate the efficiency of CNN when working as a surrogate model for the best traditional upscaling method. Otherwise, we should train the CNN considering datasets generated with all the selected methods with limited conclusions if the computational setup does not have enough generality. Hence, we consider samples from the SPE10 model besides synthetic data. Our criterion to choose layers from SPE10 model is steered by the goal of demonstrating the capabilities of CNN in upscaling tasks involving smooth and highly channelized regions. So, we start by considering layers 10, 40, 61 and 80 of the SPE10 model obtaining no conclusive results. Then, we investigate a more complete experimental setup that includes 50 channelized layers (from 36 to 85) from the SPE10 model besides synthetic data. With respect to the latter, our goal is to carry out a deeper analysis regarding performance in order to reinforce the conclusions obtained with SPE10 samples. In this way,

we generate binary channelized realizations populated with Gaussian models obtained by Karhunen-Loève (KL) expansion [21]. Continuing the preparation of the setup for comparing permeability upscaling techniques, another important point is the metric for performance evaluation. Among the techniques used for that purpose [13, 17], we have elected the relative error over the production profile because is a measure always applicable for assessing the predictive quality, and the breakthrough time because an essential point for the study of secondary recovery, which allows to evaluate the arrival of water to the producing well. Both the production curve and the breakthrough time are estimated by two-phase flow simulations (Appendix A).

Considering those metrics and computational experiments setup, the local-extended and local-global procedures no provide considerable improvement regarding local upscaling which was chosen for its simplicity and computational efficiency. Earlier studies presented in [3] reported different results when comparing with the local method. However, the upscaled property in [3] is the transmissibility and the experimental scenario is different compared with the one used in this work. Besides, the upscaled transmissibility values are restricted to the numerical method used, while the coarse permeability values obtained have a broader utility.

Hence, in the next stage, we apply the local procedure to generate the 2D and 3D datasets to calibrate and test the CNN approach. The computational results demonstrate that the CNN provides results with enough precision in less computational time compared to the local method. In addition, we performed additional tests comparing our CNN with traditional architectures, such as VGGNet and ResNet, adapted for the upscaling problem. These tests were conducted to evaluate the proximity of the results of our proposal in relation to more established architectures, allowing a detailed analysis of the performance and efficiency of the CNN developed for the upscaling problem. Therefore, the main conclusion is that the CNN can be used to accelerate simulations for decision-making in the time required by the industry.

In order to improve the performance of the GA proposed in [12], a methodology for initializing the internal parameters of the architectures generated during the GA was also incorporated, computed from the probability distribution of the weights associated with the convolutional and fully connected layers adjusted in previous generations. This approach aims to design more efficient architectures, starting from the second generation of the GA, which contributed to a more effective optimization of the process.

During the development of the work, the idea of using an autoencoder to compute the low resolution permeability field in the latent space also arose, with less computational demand than numerical procedures. We used the CNN developed via GA in [12] as the encoder component, while the decoder was configured to reflect the encoder structure, ensuring the symmetry of the encoding and decoding process. To adapt the autoencoder to our upscaling problem, the traditional loss function was adjusted to optimize the reconstruction fidelity in terms of geological characteristics.

The current conclusions are consistent with the ones achieved in [12] when comparing local and CNN approaches.

The contributions of this paper can be summarized as follows:

1. A systematic comparison between traditional (analytical and numerical) permeability upscaling techniques ;
2. Election of the local method as the best upscaling procedure in terms of relative error over the production curve and breakthrough time for generating coarse-scale models;
3. We developed a methodology for initializing the internal parameters of the CNN architectures that is more efficient than traditional methods;
4. We proposed another alternative for training the optimized CNN using an autoencoder architecture;
5. Evaluation of the performance of the CNN in comparison with the reference solution with the conclusion that the CNN can be used as a surrogate model for the local technique keeping enough precision with much less computational demand.

This work is organized as follows: In Section 2, we present the related works to the upscaling problem. Section 3 describes the methodology for selecting the best upscaling technique to generate training and validation data. The results of the traditional upscaling methods are analyzed and compared in Section 4. Following, in Section 5, are present the results of the local and CNN procedures. In Section 6 the results for the upscaling problem using our initialization approach are presented. For the autoencoder architecture the results are shown in Section 7. The discussions of the results are reported in Section 8. Next, Section 9 describes the conclusions and future works. Finally, in Appendix A, we present the equations that govern the two-phase flow.

2 Related Work

In this section we will review works that address analytical and numerical techniques to compute coarse scale parameters. In [22], the authors considered three-dimensional systems with random permeabilities, demonstrating that the geometric mean provides an appropriate approximation for the permeability. The authors of the reference [23] developed an analytical procedure for the determination of the average permeability tensor in layered systems. The work [24] presents a power averaging method for calculating the equivalent permeability for reservoirs containing a sand and shale combination, in which the power averaging exponent changes between -1 and 1. The exponents of -1, 0 and 1 result in harmonic, geometric and arithmetic averaging, respectively. Unlike previous studies, in [25] it was developed an analytical procedure, referred to as renormalization, which performs successive upscaling steps until the coarse scale block is reached. For a heterogeneous medium with large permeability variation, the method provided results comparable with numerical solution that also are significantly better than simple estimates, such as the

geometric mean. This procedure was first applied to two dimensional grids of spatially uncorrelated values. Later, it was extended to three dimensions and correlated fields [26].

In order to obtain upscaling results more accurate, the numerical methods are usually applied. In [6], the author presents a local procedure to determine the equivalent permeability tensors for heterogeneous porous media. The method consists of solving the fine scale pressure equation subject to periodic boundary conditions through finite elements. In the work [19], the authors developed an extended local method for computing the permeability at the block interfaces, which tries to reduce the effect of boundary conditions on the calculation of upscaled property. They tested the technique on a synthetic reservoir with a binary distribution of permeabilities corresponding to sand and shale, which reported better results than traditional procedures. By contrast, global methods preserve more fine scale information than local techniques, but are very expensive. The work [27] presents a global technique that seeks to preserve variance and spatial correlation within a permeability field. The authors validated the procedure in different systems and showed that it captures more structural and non-structural information of fine scale permeability fields than local methods. In [3], the authors developed a local-global method that uses information from global coarse-scale simulations to provide boundary conditions to determine the upscaled permeability. An iterative procedure ensures consistency between the local and global calculations. This method showed better coarse scale results for problems highly heterogeneous than local and extended local techniques. In this line, the work [4] shows a generalization of the local-global upscaling that involves three important aspects such as a specific flow scenario, near-well upscaling, and a thresholding procedure, showing more accurate results than extended local techniques for single and two-phase flow scenarios.

Regarding comparison between upscaling methods the reference [13] investigates the efficiency of analytical and flow-based methods applied in gas injection and waterflood problems, assessing the quality of the simulation results by the production curves. The work [16] reviews and analysis multiscale methods in terms of accuracy, robustness, computational complexity, and implementation aspects, using as a benchmark the adaptive local-global upscaling [4]. Multiscale methods are performed in different cases to calculate coarse results evaluated in terms of the reference saturation and velocity. In [17], the authors tested the arithmetic averaging and flow-based methods in three-dimensional problems to get coarsened well index using as baselines the Peaceman procedure [28]. The authors of [29] show an evaluation of different quadtree grid methods compared to uniform mesh upscaling in single-phase and multiphase flow problems. With the exception of the reference [16], all the others [13, 17, 29] present conclusions from tests performed on a single sample, which can bias the choice of the appropriate upscaling technique. However, the work [16] restricts its studies to synthetic realizations with no channels that are easier for upscaling.

Our work does not suffer from such issues since it considers realizations with channels in the main and secondary flow directions. We test a pool of upscaling methods composed by arithmetic averaging [18], local [6], local-extended [19], local-global [3] and CNN architectures developed in [12] to calculate the equivalent permeability on 2D and 3D, without solving any type of flow problems. The results show that the neural network produces better estimates than those obtained by analytical techniques with similar computational cost, but showing competitive solutions compared to the numerical approaches that are more computationally involved.

3 Methodology for Upscaling Techniques Comparison

The workflow for comparing upscaling methodologies used in this work is composed by the following steps:

1. Literature review to assemble traditional (analytical and numerical) upscaling approaches;
2. Definition of suitable datasets to perform the computational experiments;
3. Selection of metrics to evaluate the performance of upscaling techniques;
4. Execute computational tests to select the best traditional method;
5. Apply the best procedure to generate the 2D and 3D datasets to calibrate and test the CNN approaches;
6. Initialization of the internal parameters of the networks through the probability distribution;
7. Training of the optimized CNN using an autoencoder architecture;
8. Comparison between the results of the best upscaling procedure and of the CNNs.

The literature review of the first item was reported in section 2. Specifically, the works [3, 16] present comparisons between upscaling approaches in the context of interest. Considering these works, we have selected the following traditional upscaling approaches: arithmetic averaging [18], local [6], local-extended [19] and local-global [3]. Such techniques are employed in upscaling tasks and serve as a benchmark for new strategies.

Next, to implement item 2, we extract 2D fields from the SPE10 model [13] to demonstrate the influence of the upscaling factors in the accuracy of the elected methods. To investigate the robustness of the strategies, in addition to the SPE10, we also generate channelized realizations populated with Gaussian models obtained by KL expansion [21], characterized by mean and covariance function.

To evaluate the accuracy of the selected methods (item 3), we considered the oil rate error and the breakthrough time because they allow us to estimate in a simple way the discrepancy between the predictions and the reference

solutions. In upscaling, the former is computed as [17]:

$$error(q_i, \hat{q}_i) = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\|q_i - \hat{q}_i\|_2}{\|q_i\|_2}, \quad (1)$$

where n denotes the total number of time steps, q_i and \hat{q}_i are production rates calculated by fine and coarse scale simulations, respectively. Regarding breakthrough time, we performed a statistical analysis and computed the coefficient of determination (R^2), given by [30]:

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m (t_i - \hat{t}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^m (t_i - \bar{t})^2}, \quad (2)$$

where m denotes the number of realizations, t_i and \hat{t}_i are the breakthrough times estimated by fine and coarse scale simulations, respectively, and \bar{t} represents the average of the time on the fine grid.

Then, in item 4, we apply the previously selected upscaling methods to calculate the upscaled models for single-phase cases. To obtain the responses of the coarse models, we perform two-phase flow simulations (Appendix A), considering a configuration with one injection well with a constant rate, and a production well. After completing the tests, we evaluate the metrics for the production curves at the coarse and fine scales and select the best suited technique according to the production error and breakthrough time.

In order to tackle item 5, we use the best method to create 2D and 3D realizations for training and validation of the CNN architectures. The data is normalized in order to avoid values with a high order of magnitude, which can impair training. Normalization consists of a process that transforms the original data into another range of values, which is usually related to the activation functions of the hidden and output layers. This process speeds up training and allows the free parameters (weights and bias) of the network to be learned more quickly during the learning phase. To normalize the training and validation fields, we use the Min-Max technique that is given by:

$$\hat{\mathbf{X}}_i = \frac{\mathbf{X}_i - \mathbf{X}_{min}}{\mathbf{X}_{max} - \mathbf{X}_{min}} \times \mathbf{Ones}(S, N), \quad (3)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_i = \frac{\mathbf{Y}_i - \mathbf{Y}_{min}}{\mathbf{Y}_{max} - \mathbf{Y}_{min}} \times \mathbf{Ones}(\hat{S}, \hat{N}), \quad (4)$$

for $i = 1, 2, \dots, M$, where \mathbf{X}_i denotes the original field in fine scale, $\hat{\mathbf{X}}_i$ is the result of normalization, \mathbf{X}_{min} and \mathbf{X}_{max} represent the minimum and maximum values of \mathbf{X}_i , respectively, and $\mathbf{Ones}(S, N)$ represents a matrix with all elements equal to one. Analogous for $\mathbf{Y}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{\hat{S} \times \hat{N}}$ that is the coarse scale representation of \mathbf{X}_i . From the application of this normalization, the magnitudes of the input and output data will be reduced to the range between 0 and 1.

By using normalized data, the network will produce results in a smaller range than the original one.

In item 6, we adopted a strategy for initializing the internal parameters of the networks computed through two probability distributions: the first computed through the weights associated with the convolutional layers and the second calculated using the weights of the fully connected layers of the three best individuals of the previous generation. For each obtained probability distribution: compute a cumulative distribution function (CDF), inverse function of CDF, generate random numbers with uniform distribution $U \sim \mathcal{U}(0, 1)$; and Finally, apply the inverse of CDF on U .

Continuing, in item 7, we performed another alternative for training the optimized CNN using an autoencoder architecture, which computes the permeability on a coarse scale in the latent space, with lower computational cost than numerical procedures. The CNN generated in the GA phase in [12] will play the role of the encoder with the function of providing the solution on a coarse scale, while its mirrored version represents the decoder that will reproduce the result on the fine mesh.

In training that follows the procedure adopted for CNN, the objective function to be minimized to compute the low-resolution permeability field is defined as:

$$\mathcal{L}(X, \hat{X}, Y, z) = \lambda \frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M \|X_i - \hat{X}_i\|^2 + \frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M \|Y_i - z_i\|^2, \quad (5)$$

where λ is a weighting factor, X_i is the fine-scale field and \hat{X}_i is its representation provided by the decoder, Y_i is the coarse-scale field, and z_i is the autoencoder prediction in the reduced space for the coarse-mesh permeability.

Finally, we compare the parameterized CNN model obtained with the best traditional upscaling procedure. We follow the training protocol defined in [12], where the architecture is executed 5 times with 400 epochs for each scenario (2D or 3D). For each case, we measured the root mean squared error over the validation set, defined as:

$$RMSE(Y, \hat{Y}) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M \|Y_i - \hat{Y}_i\|_2^2}, \quad (6)$$

where \mathbf{Y} is the high resolution field and $\hat{\mathbf{Y}}$ that is its low resolution version computed by the CNN.

We also calculate in the validation process the average relative error:

$$e = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N RE(\mathbf{Y}_i, \hat{\mathbf{Y}}_i), \quad (7)$$

where N denotes the number of fields on the validation set, and the relative error:

$$RE(\mathbf{Y}_i, \hat{\mathbf{Y}}_i) = \frac{\|\mathbf{Y}_i - \hat{\mathbf{Y}}_i\|_2}{\|\mathbf{Y}_i\|_2}. \quad (8)$$

4 Selecting the best traditional method

Firstly, we analyze how much the coarsening on the geological grid influences the oil production profiles for the considered traditional methods: arithmetic averaging, local, local-extended, and local-global. For validation of upscaled results, we run two-phase flow simulations (Appendix A) by assuming a reservoir model, where the water is injected from the left at a constant rate and oil is produced from the right of the model, shown in the Figure 1. At the lower and upper boundaries are imposed homogeneous flow conditions and the right boundary is set with pressure equal to zero. We also assume incompressible fluids and neglect both capillary pressure and gravity effects. The porosity is assumed constant at 0.2, and the viscosity ratio is configured as $\mu_o/\mu_w = 10$. Furthermore, we set the relative permeability of water and oil as $k_{rw} = S^2$ and $k_{ro} = (1 - S)^2$, where S is the saturation of water. The initial and boundary conditions used in the simulations are presented below:

$$\begin{cases} S_w(\mathbf{x}, 0) = 0, & \forall \mathbf{x}, \\ p(\mathbf{x}, t) = 10^5 Pa, & \forall y = 440 \text{ m}, \\ \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t) \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0, & \forall x = 0 \text{ m e } x = 120 \text{ m}, \\ \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t) \cdot \mathbf{n} = G, & \forall y = 0 \text{ m}, \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

where G depends on the injection flow rate.

4.1 2D SPE10 case

To demonstrate the effects of the coarse grid on the efficiency of the procedures, we consider 2D cases that denote permeability fields attributed to the 10, 40, 61, and 80 layers of the SPE10, defined on a 60×220 geological grid. Layers 40, 61, and 80 correspond to the Upper Ness formation, which are more difficult for upscaling due to the abrupt variations in permeability and the complex connectivity introduced by the channels where the permeability varies from 0.001 to 20,000 millidarcy. In contrast, layer 10 is associated with the Tarket formation without channels, with a variation of permeability between 0.04 to 20,000 millidarcy. Figure 2 displays the selected layers of the SPE10 model.

First, we will analyze the performance of the upscaling techniques with regard to different coarse grids on various geological models. The 120×440 computation grid is kept fixed for all cases, and the 60×220 fine grid is coarsened to 30×110 , 15×55 , and 6×22 .

Results for oil production rate obtained through simulations (Appendix A) with the reference fine grid model and coarse results constructed by local method for the layer 10 are shown in Figure 3 (a). Note that the 6×22 grid has

Fig. 1 2D reservoir model with dimensions of 120×440 .

the worst error, while the other grids present similar solutions to the reference model. In Figure 3 (b), we again observe that the 6×22 grid solution obtained by local-extended with the border region ($r = 1.5$) gives the larger discrepancy compared to the fine scale solution. The 30×110 and 15×55 results given by local-global procedure using $r = 1.5$ and 2 iterations are more accurate relative to the solution on the fine grid than the 6×22 result, as shown in Figure 3 (c). For the solutions in Figure 3 (d), the visual inspection indicates that the 6×22 grid solution given by arithmetic average is more accurate than the counterparts in Figures 3 (a)-(c) which is an unexpected behavior considering the simplicity of the arithmetic average method. Regarding the prediction of the breakthrough time, all four techniques get solutions on the 30×110 grid nearby to the fine grid result.

Figure 4 (a) shows the responses along 1500 days for the reference mesh and three coarse grids constructed by the local method for the layer 40. We can see that the 15×55 grid gives a result more close to the fine grid solution up to 1250 days, showing a greater discrepancy in final oil rate compared to the 30×110 grid, which anticipates the prediction of the breakthrough time. In contrast, the 6×22 grid provides the worst prediction for the production curve. Solutions for the upscaled grids computed via the local-extended method with $r = 1.5$ and reference grid are displayed in Figure 4 (b). We may observe that as geological grid is coarsened, the solution get worse, and the 6×22 grid gives the larger error, whereas the 30×110 result provides a response more accurate than the others grids. Using the coarse grids obtained by local-global upscaling with $r = 1.5$ and 10 iterations, we obtain the solutions shown in Figure 4 (c). For the 30×110 grid, the production curve is closer to the reference compared to those generated by the remaining grids. Figure 4 (d) shows the production profile of upscaling results computed by arithmetic average. We can note that

Fig. 2 Logarithm of the permeability fields. (a) layer 10, (b) layer 40, (c) layer 61, and (d) layer 80.

the 30×110 , 15×55 , and 6×22 grids give solutions that present a lower level of agreement with the fine grid result compared with the results obtained by other techniques. In particular, the 6×22 result shows a considerable error from the reference solution. In all cases, the 6×22 grid presents the worst predictions of breakthrough time, mainly the result of the arithmetic average.

For the layer 61, the local method reached coarse scale results that presented the oil curves displayed in Figure 5 (a). Although the 30×110 and 15×55 grids achieve a good prediction for the breakthrough time, they present curves with a low level of agreement with respect to the fine scale solution. Figure 5 (b) shows that the solution in the grid 30×110 obtained by local-extended with $r = 1.5$ agrees reasonably well with the fine scale model, particularly in the final time. Again, the solution in the 30×110 grid generated by local-global with $r = 1.5$ and 10 iterations is more precise compared to other grids, as shown in Figure 5 (c). In contrast to the previous cases, the 15×55 provided by arithmetic average has a solution closer to fine scale solution, as illustrated in Figure 5 (d). Considering the breakthrough time in the plots of Figure 5, the 6×22 grid provided by the local method reaches the best estimation than the counterparts in Figures 5 (b)-(d).

Fig. 3 Fine and coarse solutions obtained by simulations for the layer 10. (a) local, (b) local-extended, (c) local-global, and (d) arithmetic.

Analogous to the before cases, we conducted experiments for the layer 80. Figure 6 (a) shows the prediction of oil rate for different coarse grids given by the local method, along with the reference solution. We can see that the solution estimated by 30×110 grid agrees reasonably with the fine grid result. All the coarse grids anticipate of the breakthrough time and their worst prediction is provided by 6×22 grid. We can observe in Figure 6 (b) that the 6×22 result provided by local-extended with $r = 1.5$ presents a lower level of agreement with the fine grid solution. In contrast, the 30×110 grid gives an approximation of the reference result that is better than the remaining grids. The response of the coarsened grid with 15×55 elements by local-global method with $r = 1.5$ and 8 iterations has the behavior farthest from the fine scale solution, as displayed in Figure 6 (c). Figure 6 (d) shows that the 30×110 grid generated by arithmetic mean gives a reasonable agreement up to 1200 days with the fine grid production curve, showing divergence at the final oil rate. As observed, the 6×22 grid gives the larger error.

Fig. 4 Fine and coarse solutions obtained by simulations for the layer 40. (a) local, (b) local-extended, (c) local-global, and (d) arithmetic.

The main results obtained using the 30×110 grid generated by different upscaling algorithms are summarized in Figure 7. It is evident that the behaviors predicted by using the approaches were not significantly different from the behavior on the fine scale for the layer 10, as shown in Figure 7 (a). For the layer 40, the local-extended is more precise than the arithmetic average and local method, particularly in the early time, as illustrated in Figure 7 (b). Although the local upscaling showed a good prediction of breakthrough time, it has a larger error compared to the local-extended upscaling on the final time for the layer 61, as displayed in Figure 7 (c). For the layer 80, the arithmetic average presented a solution closer to the fine scale result than the flow-based procedures, as shown in Figure 7 (d). In the smooth layer (Figure 7 (a)), all methods perform reasonably well, whereas for the channelized cases the arithmetic average is not as accurate as the numeric procedures, presenting larger errors, except for the layer 80 (Figure 7 (d)). Table 1 shows the relative errors (Equation 1) of the techniques for each of the scenarios. For most cases, the local-extended upscaling is the most accurate in terms of relative error, but its performance does not show a significant discrepancy compared to the local method which requires the least computational time to obtain the solution on the larger scale. Table 2 presents both the fine scale breakthrough time and

Fig. 5 Fine and coarse solutions obtained by simulations for the layer 61. (a) local, (b) local-extended, (c) local-global, and (d) arithmetic.

the corresponding ones estimated by the 30×110 models calculated using the techniques. We note that the predictions provided by the arithmetic mean have the worst times, with the exception of layer 80. For other layers, highlight for the solutions of local-global procedure that estimates values close to the reference.

Table 1 Relative errors of the approaches on the upscaling task for the 30×110 grid, with smaller values in red.

Approaches	Grid	10	40	61	80
local	30×110	0.0032	0.0326	0.0373	0.0318
local-extended	30×110	0.0031	0.0169	0.0176	0.0417
local-global	30×110	0.0032	0.0270	0.0202	0.0382
arithmetic mean	30×110	0.0058	0.1081	0.0721	0.0251

Fig. 6 Fine and coarse solutions obtained by simulations for the layer 80. (a) local, (b) local-extended, (c) local-global, and (d) arithmetic.

As shown in Table 3, for the 15×55 results, the relative errors are not as accurate as those obtained for the 30×110 models. We also observe the same result for the predictions of the breakthrough time shown in Table 4. For the 6×22 solutions, the errors are higher compared to those obtained for the 30×110 and 15×55 models, according to Table 5. Regarding the estimation of the breakthrough time, the results are also worse than those previously indicated, as shown in Table 6. We observed that the upscaled model via arithmetic mean, cannot predict the breakthrough time for the layer 61.

The best method for each layer considering the relative errors and breakthrough times previously reported is displayed in Tables 7 and 8, respectively. From those tables, we noticed variability in the performance of the methods relative to the upscaling factor and geological model, which makes it difficult to select the appropriate technique.

Fig. 7 Oil production curves for the 30×110 grid. (a) layer 10, (b) layer 40, (c) layer 61, and (d) layer 80.

For a deeper analysis, we considered 50 channelized layers (36 to 85) from the SPE10 model, instead of a single layer as performed in the previous tests. All the layers are in a fine mesh with 60×120 elements, which is coarsened by an upscaling factor of 2 in reason of the smallest error compared with the other ratios considered in the earlier cases. Figure 8 (a) reports the average reference curve computed over the 50 realizations and its corresponding coarse mesh prediction given by the upscaling procedures selected earlier. Visually, we can not perceive significant differences between the flow-based methods, except for the arithmetic mean that displays poor performance. However, on average the local procedure is the most accurate method in terms of the relative errors, as shown in Table 9. The local-extended method presents the highest R^2 value (Equation 2) for the breakthrough time, exceeding in 0.0403 the result of the local procedure, indicating minimal discrepancy, as displayed in Figure 8 (b). Figure 9 shows for each method the fit between the predictions of breakthrough times and the corresponding ones on the fine scale.

Table 2 Breakthrough time in days of the approaches on the upscaling task for the 30×110 grid, with best values in red.

Approaches	Grid	10	40	61	80
reference method	60×220	895	945	1135	980
local	30×110	900	890	1160	940
local-extended	30×110	900	930	1100	915
local-global	30×110	895	945	1150	915
arithmetic mean	30×110	890	1095	1325	995

Table 3 Relative errors of the approaches on the upscaling task for the 15×55 grid, with smaller values in red.

Approaches	Grid	10	40	61	80
local	15×55	0.0121	0.0229	0.1467	0.0528
local-extended	15×55	0.0136	0.0582	0.0716	0.0628
local-global	15×55	0.0116	0.0709	0.0880	0.0545
arithmetic mean	15×55	0.0138	0.1590	0.0207	0.0823

Table 4 Breakthrough time in days of the approaches on the upscaling task for the 15×55 grid, with best values in red.

Approaches	Grid	10	40	61	80
reference method	60×220	895	945	1135	980
local	15×55	920	965	840	920
local-extended	15×55	925	1030	975	885
local-global	15×55	920	1055	955	915
arithmetic mean	15×55	920	1160	1170	1075

We also constructed binary models with channels in the principal and secondary directions of the flow to assess the accuracy of the techniques. For each scenario, we apply the procedures over 100 binary realizations populated with random fields obtained through the KL expansion, using an exponential covariance function with different correlation lengths $\eta_1 = \eta_2 = 20$, $\eta_1 = \eta_2 = 25$, and $\sigma = 1$. Examples of fine scale models in the 60×220 grid are presented in Figure 10.

For synthetic samples, we perform 2D simulations, using the procedure of Appendix A, with the injection rate of $100 \text{ m}^3/\text{day}$ and the time of 50 days. In these scenarios, the average production profile of the upscaled models with 30×110 cells has good agreement with the fine scale solution. Table 10 shows that the local upscaling has the lower relative error compared to the other procedures, and the arithmetic average presents the worst error. As for the breakthrough time, the method reached good predictions for both synthetic cases, according with the R^2 value (Equation 2). From the results reported in Tables 9 and 10 we selected the local method to obtain the training and

Table 5 Relative errors of the approaches on the upscaling task for the 6×22 grid, with smaller values in red.

Approaches	Grid	10	40	61	80
local	6×22	0.0425	0.0652	0.0173	0.0828
local-extended	6×22	0.0453	0.1004	0.0729	0.0559
local-global	6×22	0.0451	0.1324	0.1008	0.0304
arithmetic mean	6×22	0.0208	0.2485	0.1089	0.1803

Table 6 Breakthrough time in days of the approaches on the upscaling task for the 6×22 grid, with best values in red.

Approaches	Grid	10	40	61	80
reference method	60×220	895	945	1135	980
local	6×22	940	1055	1150	875
local-extended	6×22	955	1120	1340	905
local-global	6×22	950	1175	1445	970
arithmetic mean	6×22	920	1500	-	1250

Table 7 Best method for each layer considering the relative error.

	10	40	61	80
Grid	Best	Best	Best	Best
30×110	local-extended	local-extended	local-extended	arithmetic mean
15×55	local-global	local	arithmetic mean	local
6×22	arithmetic mean	local	local	local-global

validation data due to its simplicity and computational efficiency compared to the local-extended and local-global methods.

5 Comparing local and CNN Procedures

In previous tests, we showed for different scenarios that the local method is able to upscale models with responses competitive relative to fine scale solutions and similar those given by the local-extended and local-global procedures. Thus, we use this method for constructing coarsened models to train and validate the CNN architectures. We generate 5000 realizations for 2D and the same quantity for 3D fields by means of KL expansion with the exponential covariance function, using $\eta_1 = \eta_2 = 20$, $\eta_3 = 1$, and $\sigma = 1$. The 2D and 3D models contain 50×50 , $50 \times 50 \times 4$ cells, which are coarsened to 10×10 and $10 \times 10 \times 2$ cells, respectively.

5.1 2D and 3D cases generated by KL expansion

We take the network with the smallest error discovered by the GA procedure presented in [12] for the 2D upscaling problem, and re-train it five times along 400 epochs over the training set with the RMSProp optimizer using batch

Table 8 Best method for each layer considering the breakthrough time.

	10	40	61	80
Grid	Best	Best	Best	Best
30×110	local-global	local-global	local-global	arithmetic mean
15×55	local, local-global arithmetic mean	local	arithmetic mean	local
6×22	arithmetic mean	local	local	local-global

(a)

(b)

Fig. 8 Comparison between the average response of the methods.

size of 10. This network is composed of 4 convolutional layers with 256, 256, 32 and 32 filters, respectively, and 1 fully connected layer with 100 neurons, achieving on the validation set a minimum RMSE of 0.0057 (Equation 6), and a smaller average relative error of 0.0442 (Equation 7), without using any data augmentation technique.

To compare the CNN solutions with those produced by the local procedure, we adopt in the simulations (Appendix A) an injection rate of $3 \text{ m}^3/\text{day}$ and a time of 50 days. Both techniques provide average answers computed over 100

Table 9 Relative errors and coefficient of determination of the approaches on the channelized layers from the SPE10 model, with best values in red.

Approaches	Grid	Error	R^2
local	30×110	0.0045	0.9046
local-extended	30×110	0.0122	0.9449
local-global	30×110	0.0187	0.9068
arithmetic mean	30×110	0.0712	0.6224

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Fig. 9 Correlation between the upscaled breakthrough times and the corresponding fine scale solution.

realizations of the validation set that converge to the reference result, but the CNN is faster than the local upscaling as verified next in Section 8. The CNN shows a relative error of 0.0098 (Equation 1) regarding to fine scale curve, while the local reports an error of 0.0100.

Fig. 10 Examples of fine scale models with $60 \times 220 \times 1$ cells. (a) Binary model with channels in the main direction of the flow, and (c) Binary model with channels in the secondary direction of the flow.

Similarly to the 2D cases (Section 5.1), we apply the fittest network for the 3D task designed by the GA in [12]. This network contains 5 convolutional layers with 128, 128, 128, 32 and 32 filters, respectively, and 1 fully connected layer with 200 neurons, obtaining in the best case a RMSE of 0.0197 (Equation 6), and a smaller average relative error of 0.1514 (Equation 7) over the validation set, using the Adam optimizer with a batch size of 20 on the training.

For this case, we consider an injection rate of $15 \text{ m}^3/\text{day}$ and a time of 50 days for 100 realizations, and we note that the procedures have similar production profiles that agree well with the fine scale solution. For this case,

Table 10 Relative errors and coefficient of determination of the approaches on the upscaling tasks, with best values in red.

Approaches	Grid	Principal flow	R^2	Secondary flow	R^2
local	30×110	0.0007	0.9891	0.0014	0.9784
local-extended	30×110	0.0014	0.9793	0.0019	0.9680
local-global	30×110	0.0015	0.9788	0.0018	0.9658
arithmetic mean	30×110	0.0031	0.9821	0.0072	0.7744

the CNN has a relative error of 0.0452, whereas the local upscaling shows an error of 0.0424.

6 GA and Initialization Methodology

Regarding the upscaling problem, we apply the GA implemented in [12] with our initialization and experimental parameters presented in Table 11 in the case of 50×50 to 10×10 with fields $\eta_1 = \eta_2 = 20$. The superiority of our proposal compared to the GA with the usual methods in terms of RMSE is observed, as shown in Figure 11. The blue curves represent the solutions of 3 executions of the GA with the proposed initialization, and the red curves denote the results for the GA with the traditional initializations of TensorFlow. For the same task, our proposal achieved better performance than differential evolution [31].

Table 11 GA parameters used in validating the initialization methodology.

Parameters	Values
Population size	50
Number of generations	50
crossover rate	0.70
mutation rate	0.30
elite size	10
selection method	tournament
crossover method	uniform

7 Autoencoder proposal for 2D Fields

Applying the autoencoder architecture to the permeability fields with $\eta_1 = \eta_2 = 20$ generated by the KL expansion, after 5 training runs with 400 epochs, we obtain relative errors of 0.0239 and 0.0096 for the 1000 fields in the fine and coarse scales of the validation set, respectively. In the training, the weights and biases learned in the GA phase were considered as the encoder initialization, and the decoder with internal parameters initialized through the proposal of [32]. Compared to the CNN error for the same problem, the autoencoder error was lower. Examples of fields in the coarse scale provided by the local method and in the latent space are shown in Figure 12.

Fig. 11 RMSE in terms of the number of GA generations with the initialization methods, where the blue curves represent the solutions of our proposal and the red curves denote the results for the traditional initializations.

Similar to the previous case, but disregarding the first term of the equation (5), we achieved a relative error of 4.728 for the fine-scale fields generated by the decoder, which indicates the difficulty of the autoencoder to reproduce the KL expansion solutions with the new loss function. In contrast, the autoencoder solutions converged to the results of the local method, presenting a relative error of 0.00927, smaller than the previous case considering the full loss function (Equation 5).

8 Discussion

To compare the computational time needed to obtain the production curves, we run the flow simulation of Appendix A three times with the upscaled solutions both on the 120×240 computational grid and on meshes that coincide with the size of coarse solutions. All times were acquired on an Intel Core processor with 3.6GHz CPU, 16GB RAM because we do not have an implementation of the upscaling methods in GPU. The simulation of the 6×22 grid over the coarse mesh is around 23 times faster than its execution on the computational grid. We also can see that speed of 30×110 grid is about 17 times lowest than its run on the grid on the small scale.

Regarding the upscaling process, the arithmetic mean requires less time, showing a low level of accuracy, while the local-global method has greater memory requirements, without a considerable gain in the calculation of equivalent permeability compared to the local upscaling, as displayed in Figure 8. Furthermore, the local-global method has the disadvantage of not converging for highly heterogeneous models.

Table 12 shows the comparison of CPU time required by CNN and numeric strategies to compute the upscaling of 2D and 3D geological models without channels, considering 100 realizations of each database. According to line 1 of Table 12, to upscale from 50×50 to 10×10 the local, local-extended, and local-global methods require an average time of 0.27, 0.80, and 1.85s to process each field, respectively. The corresponding time needed by CNN to get the solution on the coarse scale is 0.02s. This corresponds to a speedup of approximately a factor of 14, 40, and 93, respectively.

For the upscaling from $50 \times 50 \times 4$ to $10 \times 10 \times 2$ the local, local-extended and local-global methods require an average time of 0.83, 7.00, and 13.76s, respectively, to yield the result on the coarse grid for each field, according to line 2 of Table 12. By contrast, the corresponding time for CNN is 0.05s and, consequently, the CNN is about 17, 140, and 275 times faster than the local, local-extended, and local-global approaches, respectively. Hence, in all

Fig. 12 Gaussian fields on the coarse grid. (a), (b) Local method results, and (c), (d) Encoder solutions.

cases reported in Table 12, the network requires much less CPU time than the flow-based procedures, which would lead to significant computational savings.

Table 12 Computational average time (s) to obtain the upscaling from 50×50 to 10×10 , $50 \times 50 \times 4$ to $10 \times 10 \times 2$ for the 2D and 3D data, respectively.

CNN	CNN CPU Time	local CPU Time	local-extended CPU Time	local-global CPU Time
<i>CNN2D</i>	0.02	0.27	0.80	1.85
<i>CNN3D</i>	0.05	0.83	7.00	13.76

In [12] it is proposed the adaptations of VGG [33] and ResNet [34] with two stages, for computation of upscaling, through the changes in the input and output layers. These architectures have 34 million and 1.9 million of trainable parameters for the 2D case, respectively. For the 3D task, the quantity of parameters are 70 and 7 million, respectively. For the 2D and 3D upscaling problems, the *CNN2D* and *CNN3D* used in the previous sections display 1.1 million and 1.3 million of trainable parameters, respectively. Hence, it is obvious that our CNNs are less complex than those literature architectures considered. The VGG and ResNet networks are trained using optimizers with respective batches used in Subsection 5.1. Following our protocol, each architecture is trained 5 times, along 400 epochs each time, to assess the performance using the same computational setup of Subsection 5.1. The errors obtained over the validation set by the considered neural networks are displayed in Table 13. Note that our optimized architectures performed very much better than the literature models in all cases for both the average RMSE and the minimum average relative error (Equation 7).

Table 13 Comparing errors of two proposed CNNs with adaptations of VGG and ResNet.

Models	2D DATA		3D DATA	
	Average RMSE	Minimum Average Relative Error (e)	Average RMSE	Minimum Average Relative Error (e)
VGG	0.1346	1.000	0.1344	0.9912
ResNet	0.0340	0.1925	0.0445	0.3323
<i>CNN2D</i>	0.0067	0.0442	—	—
<i>CNN3D</i>	—	—	0.0205	0.1514

Using the alternative proposal for training the CNN designed by the GA, based on the autoencoder presented in Section 3, we obtained a model that achieved better results at the coarse scale in terms of relative error compared to the traditionally trained CNN presented in [12]. By considering in the training the loss function given by the equation (5), with $\lambda \neq 0$, the autoencoder computes a solution at the fine scale that converges to the reference. In contrast, the performance of the decoder worsens in terms of relative error by making $\lambda = 0$, that is, considering only the term of the fields at the coarse scale.

In order to improve the CNN parameterization step, we incorporated into the GA a new weight initialization methodology described in Section 3, which makes use of the weight distribution of the networks of the previous generation to generate random numbers to initialize the candidate architectures obtained by the genetic operators in the next generation.

9 Conclusion

In order to reduce the computational time of the upscaling stage, recently we designed in [12] CNN models to predict the equivalent permeability for 2D and 3D problems. However, the CNN capabilities were demonstrated in a limited scenario. So, in this paper, we first compare traditional upscaling techniques in order to select the best one to compare with our CNN approach. In this step, we carefully assemble works that present comparisons between upscaling methods to select a list of traditional approaches. Then, we specify datasets and select suitable metrics for performance evaluation. Next, our methodology includes exhaustive tests considering SPE10 samples and synthetic realizations. According to the considered metrics, the local upscaling procedure was selected as the best one in our tests. Next, CNN model and local method were compared for the 2D and 3D upscaling tasks. The experimental results show that the networks were able to predict the coarse scale permeability within the error level of Local procedure with lower CPU time, showing a factor about 14 and 17 faster than the Local technique, confirming the advantage of CNN in those tasks. Besides, compared to VGG and ResNet architectures, our CNNs provided results with better accuracy being less computationally involved than the counterparts.

Furthermore, we explored an alternative training approach using autoencoders. The CNN trained using an autoencoder was able to generate solutions in the coarse mesh with a lower average relative error than that obtained by the CNN trained in the traditional way. This demonstrates the viability and potential of this technique as an effective alternative for training in upscaling applications.

To further refine the CNN parameterization, in addition to the most efficient genetic operators, we also incorporated into the GA an initialization methodology computed on the weights adjusted in the previous generation. This approach led to the development of more accurate architectures for classification and upscaling tasks, outperforming the GA with usual procedures and differential evolution.

Acknowledgments. The authors would like to thank the financial support provided by the CAPES (Grant-88887.464658/2019-00), and the National Laboratory for Scientific Computing (LNCC/MCTI, Brazil) for providing HPC resources of the SDumont supercomputer.

Conflict of Interest. The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

Appendix A Mathematical Formulation

This section presents the formulation that governs the two-phase flow simulation to obtain production profiles.

A.1 Governing equations

For the two-phase flow in a porous media which occupies the domain Ω and boundary Γ , the Darcy law in the absence of gravity effects and capillary pressure, can expressed for phase α as:

$$\mathbf{v}_\alpha = -\mathbf{k} \frac{k_{r\alpha}(S_\alpha)}{\mu_\alpha} \nabla p, \quad (\text{A1})$$

where $\alpha = w, o$ represents the fluid phases, \mathbf{k} is the absolute permeability, $k_{r\alpha}$ is the relative permeability of phase α , μ_α denotes the viscosity of phase α , and p is the pressure.

The conservation of mass for each phase assuming incompressible fluids, rigid porous media, and without sources, is given by:

$$\phi \frac{\partial(S_\alpha)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{v}_\alpha) = 0, \quad (\text{A2})$$

where S_α is the saturation of phase α and ϕ is the porosity constant.

By summing the mass balances of the phases (Equation (A2)) and using the relationship $S_w + S_o = 1$, we get:

$$\nabla \cdot (\mathbf{v}_t) = 0, \quad (\text{A3})$$

where $\mathbf{v}_t = \mathbf{v}_w + \mathbf{v}_o$ is the total velocity.

Using the Equation (A1), we can write the total velocity as:

$$\mathbf{v}_t = \mathbf{v}_w + \mathbf{v}_o = -\mathbf{k} \gamma_t(S_w) \nabla p, \quad (\text{A4})$$

where $\gamma_t(S_w)$ is total mobility defined by:

$$\gamma_t(S_w) = \left(\frac{k_{rw}(S_w)}{\mu_w} + \frac{k_{ro}(S_w)}{\mu_o} \right). \quad (\text{A5})$$

Combining the Equations (A3) e (A4), we have the pressure equation:

$$\nabla \cdot (\mathbf{k}\gamma_t(S_w) \nabla p) = 0. \quad (\text{A6})$$

The velocity for the phase w can to be express as $\mathbf{v}_w = f(S_w)\mathbf{v}_t$, where $f(S_w)$ is the function of Buckley-Leverett fractional flow. Inserting it in the Equation (A2), we obtain the pressure equation:

$$\phi \frac{\partial(S_w)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (f(S_w)\mathbf{v}_t) = 0. \quad (\text{A7})$$

Upon solution of (A6), we obtain the saturation field by means of the finite difference method for the equation (A7):

$$\phi \frac{(S_w^{n+1} - S_w^n)}{\Delta t} + \nabla \cdot (f(S_w)^n \mathbf{v}_T^n) = 0, \quad (\text{A8})$$

$$\mathbf{v}_t^n = -\mathbf{k}\gamma_t(S_w)^n \nabla p^n, \quad (\text{A9})$$

subject to initial and boundary conditions:

$$\begin{cases} S_w(x, 0) = S_w^0(x), & \text{on } \Omega, \\ p(x, t) = \bar{p}(x), & \text{on } \Gamma_D \times (0, T], \\ \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0, & \text{on } \Gamma_N \times (0, T], \end{cases} \quad (\text{A10})$$

where Γ_D and Γ_N represent, respectively, the Dirichlet and Neumann boundary and \mathbf{n} is the normal vector.

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